

A NEW MATRIX SYSTEM FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITES:

DICYANATE SEMI-IPN

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Summary

The Allied proprietary dicyanate Semi-Interpenetrating Polymer Network (semi-IPN) system is a material which combines the advantages of both thermoplastics and thermosets. The first part of this report addresses the chemistry of our semi-IPNs and the characterization of the neat resin. All results indicate that dicyanate Semi-IPN is a good matrix candidate for high performance, high temperature fiber reinforced composites.

Two potential applications; namely, printed circuit boards and aerospace structural parts, have been developed based on Allied's proprietary semi-IPNs. As printed circuit boards for leadless chip carriers, IPN/Kevlar composites provide a lower dielectric constant, lower coefficient of thermal expansion, and better thermal microcrack resistance than epoxy/Kevlar composites. For aerospace structural applications, IPN/graphite composites possess the stiffness and toughness at various environmental conditions. The structure and performance of these applications are documented in this paper.

I. INTRODUCTION

An Interpenetrating Polymer Network (IPN) is usually defined as a combination of two polymers in network form, at least one of which is synthesized and/or crosslinked in the immediate presence of the other. There are several fairly recent reviews (1-4) of IPNs. In full IPNs, both components are crosslinked; the phases of both materials are continuous and thus interpenetrate each other. A semi-IPN is defined as a material system with two continuous phases; however, only one of the phases is crosslinked.

Allied Corporation has been investigating the dicyanate semi-IPNs for more than six years (5). Allied's dicyanate semi-IPN combines a thermoset resin (with high heat deflection temperature and good solvent resistance) with a tough thermoplastic resin, yielding a high performance, high use temperature chemically unique material system.

The Allied dicyanate semi-IPN resin has unlimited shelf life, even in the B stage or prepreg form, short curing cycles, and minimal shrinkage on curing. The low-melt viscosities allow processing at low temperatures. The curing temperatures fall in the 220°C and 300°C range without catalysts. The cured IPNs have improved impact strength, low-moisture absorption, low dielectric constant, good thermal cycling resistance, and good adhesion to fibers.

Based on these merits, Allied's proprietary dicyanate semi-IPNs are being considered for various applications, such as adhesives, coatings, electrical and electronic parts, and as a matrix resin for advanced composites. Two applications; namely, aerospace structural composites and high performance printed circuit boards (PCB), are discussed in this report.

For the aerospace industry, carbon fiber reinforced plastic composites and the associated manufacturing technology have matured to the point where they are being incorporated in primary structures. However, the low resin tensile strength and fracture toughness of the currently used thermosetting resins limit their applications (6). On the other hand, thermoplastics-based carbon fiber composites have been developed to substitute for the brittle epoxy system. Unfortunately, they still have material problems (e.g., low end-use temperature, solvent resistance) and processing problems (e.g., poor fiber-resin wetout, high processing temperatures) which remain to be solved (7). Since Allied's dicyanate semi-IPNs combine thermoplastic and thermoset, they should possess the stiffness, toughness, higher T_g , solvent resistance, and low moisture pick-up properties that are desirable for advanced composites.

Printed circuit board technology is well-established for producing leaded insertion electronic component printed wiring assemblies. The state of the art is a surface mount technology using leadless chip carriers (LCC) for the PCBs. This technology has given the electronic industry an opportunity to achieve higher packaging densities than previous dual-in-line packages (8). In order to take full advantage of this surface mount technology for high performance PCBs, a new substrate material must be developed. The ideal candidate should have a coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of +6.4 ppm/°C, a low dielectric constant; around 3.0, and better thermal shock resistance (9). Again, consideration was given to Allied's semi-IPN because of its flexibility and higher T_g .

II. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

In this report, the dicyanate of bisphenol-A (2-CBA) was used as the thermoset component for the semi-IPNs. Generally, dicyanates can be synthesized from any compound containing two phenolic groups by reaction with cyanogen bromide in the presence of an acid acceptor (10). The reaction is shown in the following equation:

Where Ar is an aromatic group.

Polyethersulfone (PES, VICTREX® from ICI Americas, Inc.) and Allied's proprietary polyester carbonate resin, COPECTM*, were selected as the thermoplastic component in the IPN system for the advanced composites. COPECTM is an experimental copolymer and its details were discussed by Bruce DeBona et. al. (11-12). For the PCB samples, polycarbonate (PC, Lexan® from G.E.) was selected as the thermoplastic component.

Methylene chloride was used to dissolve the thermoplastic resin and 2-CBA. In order to optimize the ratio between thermoplastics and 2-CBA, various combinations were used. Sized and unsized carbon fibers from various suppliers were used as reinforcements for the advanced composites. For the PCBs, the reinforcing material was DuPont's Kevlar®-49 fabric with an areal density of 1.75 oz/yd².

2.2 Prepregging

The dicyanate semi-IPNs are made in a two-step process. In the first step, the chosen thermoplastic and monomeric dicyanate of bisphenol-A (2-CBA) are mixed in methylene chloride to form a solution. The method used to make the thermoplastic/2-CBA mixture is not critical. They can be mixed by hand in a flask, in batch mixers, or even in an extruder. This thermoplastic/2-CBA mixture (without solvent) is a non-tacky solid at room temperature. Also, it has an infinite shelf life since the 2-CBA does not crosslink at room temperature.

Since both applications involve composite materials (i.e., IPN/carbon fiber and IPN/Kevlar® fabric), a good fiber wetout is critical to the composite performance. A solution coating should give a satisfactory degree of wetout between fiber and resin. The unidirectional carbon fiber/IPN prepreg was prepared by filament winding techniques. The IPN/Kevlar® prepreg was prepared by dipping the fabric into the solution for about 2 minutes. All prepregs were dried in a vacuum oven at 60°C overnight.

* Experimental Material

2.3 Curing & Molding

In order to obtain the semi-IPNs, the solvent-free thermoplastic/2-CBA mixture has to be heated to a temperature where the monomeric dicyanate crosslinks. The cure temperature varies from 220°C to 300°C. The cure time of the thermoplastic/2-CBA mixture depends on the cure temperature, catalyst, and catalyst level. For instance, uncatalyzed 2-CBA cures in 30 minutes at 270°C while highly catalyzed material cures in about 1 minute at 300°C. On the other hand, a highly catalyzed 2-CBA can be fully cured at 200°C for longer time.

Figure 1 shows the dicyanate crosslinking reaction. The dicyanates crosslink to form thermally stable triazine rings without evolution of volatiles.

In order to obtain composite laminates, layers of the non-tacky preregs were laid in a 6" x 6" die for molding using a hot press. The molding temperature was 270°C and curing time (i.e., for 2-CBA) was around 30 minutes before being cooled down between the water-cooled platens.

It is recognized that these processing conditions were designed only for laboratory-scale runs. A well-defined processing profile is needed for commercial production. The curing temperature and time can be reduced significantly by adding catalysts to the IPN system.

Figure 1. Trimerization of Dicyanates to Form a Network

2.4 Characterization

Most measurements were conducted in accordance with ASTM testing standards. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) was used to measure the glass-transition temperature (T_g) of the semi-IPNs. Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) was used to determine the thermal stability. The ASTM specification D1525 was used to determine the Vicat softening temperatures at two penetrations; namely 25 μ M and 1000 μ M.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of this report are divided into the following categories for discussion.

3.1 Neat Resin Properties

The tensile properties of semi-IPNs of 2-CBA with various thermoplastics are listed in Table I. The weight ratio between 2-CBA and thermoplastic is 1 to 1. The corresponding properties for the pure thermoplastic resins are also given. It is concluded that these dicyanate IPNs are strong and have surprisingly high elongations to break even though their cross-linking densities are high.

Table I
TENSILE PROPERTIES OF THERMOPLASTIC/2-CBA
(EQUAL WEIGHT) SEMI-IPNs

<u>Material</u>	<u>B.E. (%)</u>	<u>Tensile Strength (psi)</u>	<u>Tensile Modulus (psi)</u>
Polycarbonate/2-CBA	17.3	12,300	299,000
Polycarbonate	11.0	9,000	345,000
Polysulfone/2-CBA	12.7	10,600	297,000
Polysulfone	50-100	10,200	360,000
Polyethersulfone/2-CBA	9.6	10,400	340,000
Polyethersulfone	30-80	12,200	350,000

Table II summarizes the 1% weight loss temperature (by TGA) and T_g (by DSC) results for the semi-IPN of 2-CBA with polycarbonate and polysulfone (equal weight). The properties for the pure thermoplastics are also listed for comparison.

As one can see from the TGA results, the thermal stability of dicyanate semi-IPNs is good. We believe that the low 1% weight loss temperature of polysulfone and its semi-IPN was caused by the loss of volatiles, such as moisture, from the sulfone. It does not reflect any chemical decomposition at such temperatures.

Table II
THERMAL PROPERTIES OF SEMI-IPNs

<u>Material</u>	<u>1% Weight Loss Temperature (°C)</u>	<u>T_g (°C)</u>
Polycarbonate/2-CBA	400	195
Polycarbonate	425	152
Polysulfone/2-CBA	350	185
Polysulfone	300	188
Cured 2-CBA	410	245

The thermo-mechanical properties of dicyanate semi-IPNs were also measured as listed in Table III. The Vicat softening temperatures provide a way of estimating at what temperatures the modulus of the semi-IPN starts to fall. All semi-IPNs in these tables consist of equal thermoplastic and 2-CBA weights.

The 25 μ M penetration temperatures of the semi-IPNs are 25 to 65°C higher than those of the corresponding pure resins. For the 1000 μ M penetration temperatures, the differences between semi-IPNs and pure resins are even greater. This shows that once the thermoplastics start to soften, they lose strength rapidly. In contrast to this, the softening of the dicyanate semi-IPNs occurs much slower since the crosslinking structure is trying to hold the system together.

Table III
VICAT SOFTENING TEMPERATURES OF SOME
DICYANATE SEMI-IPNs AND THEIR COMPONENTS

<u>Material</u>	<u>25μM Penetration Temperature (°C)</u>	<u>1000μM Penetration Temperature (°C)</u>
Polycarbonate/2-CBA	201	>250*
Polycarbonate	135	155
Polysulfone/2-CBA	188	>250*
Polysulfone	165	189
Cured 2-CBA	-	>250*

*Testing equipment limit

3.2 IPN/Carbon Fiber Advanced Composites

Figures 2 and 3 are SEM pictures for the fracture surface of IPN/carbon fiber composites. The degree of wetout between resin and fiber was satisfactory. Since IPN resins need to be cured at 270°C, few sizing chemicals are suitable as a result of thermal stability limitations. It is concluded from our study that an unsized carbon fiber is preferred for IPN-based composites. In addition, voids appeared on none of the samples indicating the molding procedures we have established are acceptable.

Figure 2. Cross-section SEM picture of IPN/carbon fiber composites.

Figure 3. SEM picture of the fracture surface of IPN/carbon fiber composite.

Table IV summarizes the flexural properties of samples prepared with different PES/2-CBA ratios. Based on this preliminary result, it is found that the stiffness decreases as the thermoplastic content increases as expected. To reach a balance between stiffness and toughness, a composition weight ratio of 50/50 between thermoplastic and 2-CBA was used for samples for other property evaluations.

Table IV
Flexural Properties of Samples
With Different PES/2-CBA Ratios

<u>Properties</u>	<u>Sample #1</u>	<u>Sample #2</u>	<u>Sample #3</u>
Density (gm/cc)	1.596	1.562	1.545
PES/2-CBA	30/70	50/50	70/30
V_f (%)	58.4	53.0	49.0
Flexural Strength (10^3 psi)	267.3	296.0	190.0
Flexural Modulus (10^6 psi)	18.3	17.1	13.2
Normalized* Flexural Strength (10^3 psi)	284	346	240
Normalized* Flexural Modulus (10^6 psi)	19.4	20.0	16.7

*62% V_f

Properties of samples based on COPECTM resin are listed in Table V. In order to better evaluate the IPN composites, data of two epoxy-based carbon fiber composites are also listed. Generally speaking, at room temperature, the performance of IPN/carbon is as good as (or even better than) the standard epoxy/carbon fiber composites. Both Izod impact and G_{IC} (Mode I by Double Cantilever beam) tests show that IPN/carbon composites have better toughness than standard epoxy. The water absorption was measured by placing samples in an environmental chamber at 95% relative humidity and 70°C for 30 days. Measured water intake for all IPN-based composites was lower than for conventional epoxy-based composites.

The temperature effect on flexural properties is shown in Table VI. It is concluded that the property retention of IPN/carbon fiber composites is as good as standard epoxy-based composites.

Table V
Properties of IPN/Carbon Fiber
 Composites Based on COPEC Resin

<u>Sample</u>	<u>COPEC/IPN¹</u>	<u>5208 Epoxy¹</u>	<u>COPEC/IPN²</u>	<u>3502 Epoxy²</u>
Ratio	30/70	-	50/50	-
Tensile Strength (10 ³ psi)	300	240	-	-
Tensile Modulus (10 ⁶ psi)	20	21	-	-
Normalized ³ Flexural Strength (10 ³ psi)	350	257	277	260
Normalized ³ Flexural Modulus (10 ⁶ psi)	18	19.7	18.8	18.5
Short-Beam Shear (10 ³ psi)	12.3	13.5	-	-
Izod Impact (KJ/m ²)	100	67	-	-
G _{IC} (in-lbs/in ²)	-	-	3.65	0.5
Water Absorption (% by weight)	0.4	0.59	-	-

Where: 1. Used Celion 6K carbon fibers
 2. Used Hercules AS-4 carbon fibers
 3. 62% V_f

Table VI
Flexural Properties of IPN
 Composites at Elevated Temperatures

<u>Sample</u>	<u>COPEC IPN*</u>	<u>3502 Epoxy</u>
Fiber	AS-4	AS-4
Normalized Flexural Strength @ RT (10 ³ psi)	277	260
Normalized Flexural Modulus @ (10 ⁶ psi)	18.8	18.5
Normalized Flexural Strength @ 350°F (10 ³ psi)	187	190
Normalized Flexural Modulus @ 350°F (10 ⁶ psi)	18.0	18.0

*COPEC/2-CBA ratio 50/50

3.3 IPN/Kevlar PCBs

The most critical requirement for Kevlar-based PCBs is the microcrack resistance during the thermal cycling test as described by D. Packard (8). After several screening tests, we concluded that a 50/50 combination of polycarbonate and 2-CBA IPN reinforced Kevlar PCB was the best system; it showed no surface microcracks after being subjected to ten cycles at -15°C to 100°C. Table VII summarizes the results of IPN/Kevlar samples for PCB applications. Based on the comments from industry leaders, lower coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) (Z-axis) and satisfactory dielectric constant and dissipation factor. However, due to the limited molding experience we had on this application, samples showed surface voids and low resin content (35-40 wt. %). These two factors were responsible for the failure in the flammability tests and time to blister at 550°F tests.

Table VII
Property List of IPN/Kevlar PCBs*

<u>Property</u>	<u>Results</u>
Flammability (UL-94)	V-1
Dielectric Constant	2.8-3.3
Dissipation Factor	0.014-0.019
Surface Resistance	1.2×10^6
Volume Resistivity	267×10^6
Arc Resistance	154
T _g (°C)	212
Z-axis CTE (ppm/°C)	
60-110°C	69
140-180°C	131
210-250°C	265
TGA weight loss (%)	
RT - 200°C	1.42
RT - 280°C	1.75

*Polycarbonate/2-CBA of 50/50 ratio

IV. CONCLUSION

IPNs are attractive because they allow the combination, in network form, of two otherwise non-compatible polymers. Allied's dicyanate semi-IPNs combine a thermoset resin with a tough thermoplastic. They are high performance, high use temperature, and chemically unique plastics. They show great strength and toughness relative to conventional thermosets, and also superior processing, chemical, and heat-resistance properties relative to thermoplastics. With all these merits, the dicyanate semi-IPNs can be used in various markets, such as adhesive, coating, electrical, electronics, and aerospace applications.

Currently, we have IPN/carbon fiber composites under extensive evaluations; such as solvent resistance, properties after moisture pick-up, etc. For the IPN/Kevlar PCBs, we are developing optimized molding conditions that will eliminate the surface voids and retain a high resin content (65%). Also, a pilot-plant scale fabrication facility of these applications is under investigation.

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